

Each graph represent the diff for the migration of **one** program (name as title of window). The first version is the delivery, and the second is the redelivery

Base graph elements: node and edge

Colors in graphs: diff highlights

Line thickness: Variation in probabilities

Particularities: fused and first-seen nodes

